

FINITE ELEMENT FATIGUE STRESS MODELLING FOR LARGE VACUUM CHAMBER

A Numerical Study for
Fatigue-resistant design

Redacted version

*For full report, please contact Guardian R&D team in the headquarter of
Guardian Europe S.à.r.l. in Bertrange, Luxembourg*

MSc thesis

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Funded by Guardian® Industries

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FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
TECHNOLOGY
AND MEDICINE

Department of Engineering

Master of Science in Civil Engineering - Megastructure Engineering with
Sustainable Resources

Master Thesis

by

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FINITE ELEMENT FATIGUE STRESS MODELLING FOR LARGE VACUUM CHAMBER

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Summary

This study investigates the fatigue behaviour of large rectangular vacuum chambers under cyclic atmospheric pressure. Predominantly, the entry/exit vacuum chamber experiences variable loading and is susceptible to fatigue-induced cracking. Such cracks compromise the airtightness of the chamber, leading to increased energy consumption for vacuum generation and reduced production capacity. Moreover, these fatigue damages jeopardize the structural integrity, raising safety concerns. A 3D model of these chambers was developed and subjected to finite element analysis. The model's validity was ensured through comparisons of vertical displacement, hotspot locations, and crack patterns. A subsequent sensitivity analysis and topology optimization were conducted to re-design the vacuum chamber, alleviating stress concentrations at identified hotspots. The fatigue performance of the re-designed chamber was evaluated using shell-to-shell and shell-to-solid sub-models with refined meshing, through structural hotspot stress and linear elastic fracture mechanics methods. The re-designed model demonstrated a substantial improvement, boasting a fatigue life 45 times that of the original chamber. Furthermore, the fatigue life in the identified fatigue-prone zones increased 24-fold on average. Not only is the re-designed chamber lid slightly lighter, but it also effectively mitigates fatigue-induced cracking, resulting in enhanced operational lifespan. This study underscores the benefits of a fatigue-resistant approach that maintains airtightness, improves energy efficiency, increases plant capacity, and obviates safety risks associated with fatigue damage. This strategy could have significant implications for industries that employ large vacuum chambers.

Keywords:

Fatigue analysis, Fracture mechanics, Vacuum chamber, Finite element analysis, Crack growth, Numerical study, Topology optimization, Hot spot

Preface

This thesis signifies the successful end of my Master of Science program in Civil Engineering at the University of Luxembourg. It was written during my time as an R&D intern at Guardian Industries, which took place from March to September 2023.

The primary thrust of this study is to extend the fatigue life of entry/exit vacuum chambers within glass production facilities. Under the unwavering guidance of **Dr. Herbert Lage**, my supervisor from Guardian Industries, the finite element models of these chambers were created. His supervision at the Guardian Industry headquarters and glass plant was invaluable to the successful development of the 3D models specific to these vacuum chambers. I express my sincere gratitude to Dr. Lage for his unwavering support and guidance.

In developing and validating the finite element models, the input of my academic supervisor from the University of Luxembourg, **Dr. Slawomir Kedziora**, was indispensable. His keen oversight during our regular weekly meetings significantly contributed to the progress of the modelling. He provided key guidance on accurately modelling different parts while managing the computational demands. I am deeply grateful to Professor Dr. Kedziora for his steadfast assistance and expert guidance.

Professor Dr. Markus Schäfer, my academic supervisor from the University of Luxembourg, efficiently forged the vital link between industry and academia. His role in the selection of appropriate simulation tools and in project timeline management was instrumental. His innovative ideas greatly enhanced the fatigue-resistant design of the entry/exit vacuum chamber, ensuring reliable connections between components. I owe a debt of gratitude to Professor Dr. Schäfer for his inspirational ideas and for managing the intersection of industry and academia seamlessly.

Lastly, my profound appreciation goes to **Guardian® Industries**. Not only did they entrust me with this project, but they also generously funded my entire master's program through the Guardian Glass Scholarship. Their trust and support played a significant role in the successful completion of this thesis.

Shahin NEJATI
Luxembourg, September 2023

Author contribution statement

This study has been entirely conducted and reported by the author, Shahin NEJATI, with the exception of the following aspects:

- The 3D model of the second-generation entry/exit vacuum chamber was created by a third-party company, while the author developed the FE model and conducted the re-design.
- The Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) procedures and visual inspections of fatigue cracks at the Czestochowa plant in Poland were undertaken by personnel from Guardian Industries and external contributors.
- The deflection measurements required for validation purposes were carried out by the engineering team at Guardian Industries.
- The computational framework, inclusive of the methodology for FE simulation, was designed under the guidance and supervision of Dr. Slawomir Kedziora.
- The review and proofreading of this report were conducted by Dr. Herbert Lage and Dr. Slawomir Kedziora.
- The re-design draws inspiration from the insights of Prof. Dr. Schäfer, Dr. Kedziora, Dr. Lage, and the expertise of the Guardian Engineering Team.

Shahin NEJATI
Luxembourg, September 2023

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List of Acronyms

The following is an alphabetically ordered list of acronyms that have been utilized throughout this thesis:

CAFL	Constant Amplitude Fatigue Limit
CFRP	Carbon Fibre–Reinforced Polymer
FAT _x	S-N curve class, where x is the fatigue strength in MPa at 2 million cycles
FE	Finite Element
GMAW	Gas Metal Arc Welding
HAZ	Heat Affected Zone
IIW	International Institute of Welding
LEFM	Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics
LSE	Linear Surface Extrapolation
MPC	Multi Point Constraint
NDT	Non-destructive Testing
PT	Penetrant Testing
SIF	Stress Intensity Factor
TSA	Thermoelastic Stress Analysis
TTSD	Through Thickness Stress Determination
UIT	Ultrasonic Impact Treatment
UP	Ultrasonic Peening
3D	Three-Dimensional
3PB	Three-Point Bending

List of Notations

a	Depth of crack
C	Paris' law material constant
$f(t)$	Thickness reduction factor
f_y	Yield stress of steel
K	Stress intensity factor
m	Paris' law material constant
N	Number of Cycle
t	Thickness of the plate
t_{eff}	Effective thickness
da/dN	Rate of fatigue crack growth
ΔK	Range of stress intensity factor
ΔK_{eff}	Range of effective stress intensity factor
ΔK_I	Range of stress intensity factor in mode I
ΔK_{II}	Range of stress intensity factor in mode II
σ_{hs}	Stress at hot spot
$\sigma_{0.4t}$	Stress at distance of 0.4×thickness from the hot spot
$\sigma_{1.0t}$	Stress at distance of 1.0×thickness from the hot spot

1. Introduction

Vacuum chambers, designed to establish and sustain a low-pressure environment while withstanding atmospheric pressure, come in various shapes and sizes, including cylindrical, spherical, and rectangular forms. In a production line featuring multiple vacuum chambers, only the entry and exit chambers undergo cyclic atmospheric pressure. This cyclical loading makes these particular chambers prone to fatigue cracks. Conversely, the central chambers, which are subject to constant atmospheric pressure with minimal variation, are largely immune to fatigue damage.

Cracks in these chambers not only shorten their lifespan but also escalate operational costs by compromising the chamber's airtightness. This leakage necessitates additional energy consumption to lower the air pressure, thereby increasing cycle times and slowing down the production line. As the number and length of cracks grow, fatigue repair becomes unavoidable. Typically, weld repair is employed as the most feasible solution for plated structures with complex geometry due to its accessibility and convenience.

However, these repairs often prove to be temporary solutions, as the welding process creates an additional Heat Affected Zone (HAZ), rendering the component more vulnerable to subsequent fatigue damage. After two or three major weld repairs, the replacement of the entry/exit chambers becomes inevitable due to the increasing frequency of required weld repairs. Furthermore, these structural maintenance procedures disrupt the production line, thereby diminishing the plant's production capacity.

Most importantly, fatigue damage threatens the structural integrity of the vacuum chamber, posing a risk to the safety of plant personnel, especially during maintenance periods when workers are required to operate within the chambers. Enhancing the fatigue performance of vacuum chambers not only extends their lifespan but also mitigates safety concerns, conserves energy, and boosts production capacity.

A low-pressure environment can significantly alter the fatigue behaviour of metallic structural components. Without oxygen and adsorbates, the area adjacent to a fresh crack undergoes increased plastic strain during the slip stage. This leads to changes in dislocation behaviour and retardation in crack propagation [1]. Research by Yoshinaka et al. [2] demonstrated that ultra-high vacuum conditions can considerably decelerate crack growth rates, notably in a small crack regime. Even in a vacuum, the presence of inert gases such as argon can accelerate the crack propagation rate, likely due to physical adsorption on the newly-formed slip stage at the crack tip, thereby underscoring the significant role of the ambient environment in the mechanism of crack growth.

In entry/exit chambers, one side of the steel plate consistently interacts with air, while the other side experiences medium vacuum intermittently. Consequently, the beneficial impact of vacuum conditions on the fatigue behaviour of the chamber is conservatively disregarded.

Given the intricate geometry of rectangular vacuum chambers, the path of load transfer is complex, and multi-axial stress states are unavoidable. However, since the point and direction of loading remain constant during the pump-down process, the entry/exit vacuum chambers experience proportional multi-axial fatigue loading. This implies that stress components persist in a consistent phase, proportionally fluctuating to one another under cyclic loading. Despite their importance, multi-axial fatigue analysis of the welded connections is not thoroughly addressed in most available codes.

Mei et al. [3] provide a comprehensive comparison of differing approaches put forth by EN 1993-1-9 [4], International Institute of Welding (IIW) Recommendations [5], and ASME VIII Div 2 Code [6]. For example, IIW recommends the use of maximum principal stress in situations with proportional stress states. However, in other circumstances, a combination effect should be considered, necessitating separate evaluations of normal and shear stress.

Numerous studies, encompassing both numerical and experimental approaches, have been conducted to investigate fatigue assessments in various structural systems, such as ships [7], aircrafts [8], bridges [9], pressure vessels [10], wind turbines [11] and LNG tanks [12]. However, a comprehensive examination of the fatigue behaviour of large rectangular vacuum chamber structures utilizing FE modelling has not been documented in the existing literature. This study introduces a FE model that has been optimized to provide accurate results while minimizing computational demand and cost. The model's accuracy has been validated using data obtained from two real-world factories each having undergone operational cycles of 10 and 14 million. The application of shell-to-shell and shell-to-solid sub-modelling techniques is evaluated for the fatigue assessment of vacuum chambers using both hot spot and fracture mechanics methodologies. In addition to this, further exploration is conducted on various design details that are commonly employed to augment the fatigue life of structures.

2. Scope and Aims of Thesis

In this study, a scalable 3D model of the entry/exit chamber is constructed based on available 2D CAD files, in-situ measurements, and an inventory list of the components, using Autodesk Inventor® software [13]. The 3D models are then geometrically pre-processed for Finite Element (FE) analysis through ANSYS® SpaceClaim [14] software. During this step, the model is checked for any over constraints and detachments.

To reduce the computational demand of the FE analysis for the large vacuum chamber, the mid-surfaces of the thin steel plates are extracted for further shell analysis. Components are interconnected using the shared topology technique, while thick plates and components with complex geometries are modelled as solid bodies.

After preparation for FE analysis, the pre-processed model is imported into ANSYS® Mechanical [15] simulation software. The supports are represented through remote displacement, while the connection to the adjoining chamber is implicitly modelled by fixing the bolt holes. Atmospheric pressure is applied to all surfaces interfacing with the low-pressure environment. A frictional contact, with a coefficient of 0.2, is defined between the chamber lid and body.

Linear hexahedron elements are employed for meshing the solid portions, and 4-node quadrilateral shell elements with 6 degrees of freedom are utilized for meshing the surface bodies within the global model. Based on a mesh sensitivity analysis, different mesh sizes are adopted for various models serving different purposes. The mesh sizes range between 10 and 50 mm across different models. These include models created for fatigue analysis—either sub-models or global models with local mesh refinement, solid sub-models for fracture mechanics analysis, and the global model for re-designing purposes.

The results of this FE analysis are validated through comparisons with observed crack patterns and deflection measurements. The deflection predicted by the FE analysis is benchmarked against measurements taken at the plant during the pump-down process. The measurements indicate a vertical displacement of 5.70 mm in the bottom plate of the chamber body, aligning closely with the 6.08 mm displacement predicted by the FE analysis.

Additionally, the locations of the identified hot spots correspond well with the existing fatigue cracks observed in vacuum chambers at two separate plants. It is important to note that only primary cracks are used for this validation, as this study does not discuss the impact of cracks and subsequent load redistribution.

This model is used to examine the structural integrity of the vacuum chamber to address the safety concerns over possible failure of the chamber due to existing fatigue damages during maintenance. The fatigue damages are implicitly modelled, and the numerical model is simulated under gravity loading to evaluate the structural safety during overhaul while the chambers are open. The effect of existing cracks and possible safety hazards are discussed herein.

There are hydraulic jacks affixed to the chamber for opening the lid during routine maintenance. Despite being designed primarily for lid manipulation and not for withstanding atmospheric pressure, these jacks significantly influence stress distribution during pump-down due to their considerable stiffness. The effect of engagement of the vacuum chamber rod is discussed after simulation of ‘engaged’ and ‘released’ conditions. The advantages and disadvantages of both conditions are pointed out in terms of susceptibility to fatigue damage.

The fatigue behaviour of the entry/exit vacuum chambers is examined using the hot spot method in accordance with the guidelines provided by IIW [5], along with Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM). These methods permit the explicit consideration of stress concentrations, thus offering a relatively high degree of precision for structures with complex geometry that are analysed via FE modelling. The structural hot spot stress is calculated using the Linear Surface Extrapolation (LSE) method. S-N curve¹ classes FAT 90² and FAT 100 are used for the fatigue analysis of welded parts, and FAT 160 for unwelded parts. The analysis assesses the components under high-cycle conditions, while the effect of corrosion on fatigue analysis is not taken into account. Both the mean stress effect and wall thickness are considered in accordance with IIW recommendations [5].

A re-design for improved fatigue resistance is conducted to extend the lifespan of the entry/exit vacuum chambers under cyclic atmospheric pressure loading. The primary focus of this re-design effort is to decrease stress levels at hotspots located in welded parts, which in turn extends the fatigue life of the vacuum chamber. The fatigue-resistant design not only lengthens the chamber's operational life, but also minimizes energy consumption by ensuring the airtightness of the vacuum chamber. This strategy assists in maintaining plant production capacity by reducing pump-down time and eliminating the necessity for regular fatigue repair, thus avoiding disruptions to the production line. Significantly, the fatigue-resistant re-design ensures the chamber's structural integrity, addressing safety concerns related to potential fatigue damage.

¹ S-N curve is a graph which shows the relationship between stress range (S) and the number of cycles which to lead to failure (N) for a given material or structural detail under cyclic loading.

² FATx classifies an S-N curve, where 'x' denotes the fatigue strength in MPa at 2 million cycles.

3. Literature review

Several vacuum chambers in the plants exhibit signs of fatigue damage, necessitating repairs to restore both their structural integrity and the airtightness essential for their operation. Choosing the correct repair method can extend the operational lifespan of these chambers. Numerous methods are available in the existing literature for fatigue repair of different materials and structural details. This section critically examines the literature on various techniques for repairing fatigue damage in different structural details and provides a tabulated assessment of their effectiveness

3.1. General

Fatigue crack initiation is a significant concern in a variety of applications, particularly in aerospace, automotive, and civil engineering, where cyclic loading can cause material damage accumulation. Insufficient consideration and important changes in the fatigue load will lead to cracks, which can compromise the structural integrity and propagate until complete failure occurs. Regular inspections are necessary to identify and monitor critical fatigue cracks, allowing for immediate repair and maintenance to prolong the lifespan of the structure. This review aims to discuss the possible methods for repairing fatigue damage and their effectiveness. To achieve this, accessible literature was categorized based on proposed solutions for repair, and a summary of each method's application is presented. This study also presents a systematic tabulation of the effectiveness of the fatigue repair methods examined in the studies reviewed. This provides a reference for engineers and researchers seeking effective methods for addressing fatigue damage in different contexts.

3.2. Fatigue damage repair in structural metals

The occurrence of fatigue damage in materials and structures due to cyclic loading is perceived as an inevitable phenomenon in a damage-tolerant approach. In many engineering applications, guaranteeing a completely fatigue-free performance over the system's entire lifespan is often impractical, not just technically but also economically. The need for highly specialized materials, meticulous design, and rigorous manufacturing processes to achieve extremely low stress concentrations required for fatigue-free performance might result in costs becoming prohibitively high. As a result, the focus in engineering is often on managing and mitigating fatigue risk rather than attempting to eliminate it entirely.

Given that fatigue-induced cracks are an expected consequence, conducting regular inspections becomes pivotal to identify potential fatigue cracks in the structures. The importance of crack detection escalates in systems such as vacuum chambers, pressure vessels, nuclear plant pipes, and ships, where crack formation might trigger system leaks, compromising not only the structural integrity of the system but also its optimal operational performance.

Once the cracks are detected, it is crucial to deploy appropriate repair strategies, accounting for factors such as the material type, the crack location's geometry, the damage extent, and the system's function.

Selecting and implementing suitable fatigue damage repairs can effectively enhance the system's lifespan.

A noted approach to improving fatigue behaviour is to decrease stress concentration. While a general correlation between fatigue strength and steel grade suggests that fatigue strength improves with increasing steel grade [16], it has been argued that the fatigue strength of welded elements does not depend on yield strength due to the presence of micro-cracks initiated during the welding process [17].

The start and stop points of the welding normally causes high stress concentration and contain weld defects and induce high residual stress [18]. This stress concentration can be reduced by reshaping the start-stop points through grinding process.

Given the prohibitive costs of experimental tests, they are not feasible for every scenario. Instead, numerical models, validated by these tests, are used to predict remaining fatigue life and crack growth. These models also compare repair methods to identify the best strategy for fatigue crack repair. Rodríguez-Sánchez et al. [19] employed fracture mechanics in repaired joints, focusing on the utilization of Y factors. The proposed method predicts fatigue life post-crack removal, validated against T-butt specimen data, and extends to predict the life of repaired tubular joints.

Predicting the fatigue life of repaired structural components can be accomplished using fatigue design codes [20]. Once the fatigue damage manifest itself through cracks across the system the calculation of remaining fatigue life of the system requires application of complicated procedures such as Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM). The application of LEFM presents challenges for practical applications. Theories of linear elastic fracture mechanics are primarily developed for small cracks, and their application requires various parameters, such as material properties and stress intensity factors [21]. These often necessitate fatigue testing and detailed numerical modelling [22].

On the other hand, there is no efficient method to estimate the remaining fatigue life of a system once it has been repaired for fatigue damage. As a result, determining the fatigue life of repaired structures and comparing it to the remaining fatigue life of unrepaired structures is not possible without comprehensive fatigue testing and numerical modelling. To address this, this study compiles various fatigue repair techniques, discuss the prevalent methods, and ultimately assesses their effectiveness in comparison to the residual life of damaged, non-repaired structures.

3.2.1. Fatigue repair via welding

Welding is often the most straightforward and readily available method for repairing fatigue cracks. However, this technique introduces a Heat Affected Zone (HAZ), which can negatively impact the fatigue performance of the structural details. The welding process induces residual stress, which can be quantified through various experimental methods or computed numerically [23].

Akyel et al. [18] examined the fatigue behaviour of weld-repaired cracks in high-strength steel, specifically grades S690 and S890. The researchers artificially created initial cracks, which were then repaired using flux-cored arc welding. While the weld-repaired crack does not conform to any category

in EN 1993-1-9 [4], the test results closely aligned with the S-N curve provided for the 'detail category' of 160. This category represents the highest fatigue strength for a simple plate with no welding or base material and is independent of steel grades. The 'detail category' number in EN 1993-1-9 [4] signifies the nominal stress range at 2 million cycles. The fatigue strength curve can be plotted using a log-log relationship between the nominal stress range and the number of cycles leading to failure, with a constant slope of $m=-3$. The study concluded that repairing the crack had a minimal adverse effect on the fatigue strength of high-strength steel. However, it is important to note that the initial cracks in this study were not induced by fatigue. Similarly, Pijpers [24] discovered that the fatigue crack initiation life of welded elements made from high-strength steel is longer than that of mild steel.

In another study, Zhang et al. [25] assessed the impact of a buffer layer on the fatigue crack growth of high-strength low-alloy steel repaired by welding. Their findings suggest that a 4-mm buffer layer enhances fatigue resistance by mitigating the adverse effects of the heat-affected zone.

Li et al. [26] conducted a study on the potential use of interior fillet welds to repair fatigue-cracked rib-to-deck joints in orthotropic steel deck bridges. The application of interior fillet welds was carried out using automated robotic welding, a realistic approach for damaged bridge repair. The results indicated that this method could enhance the fatigue life of the joints by a factor of 5 to 8 times more than the remaining fatigue life of unrepaired specimens.

3.2.2. Fatigue repair via rewelding in welded structures

Nascimento and Voorwald [27] evaluated the impact of welding and rewelding (both first and second instances) on AISI 4130 steel. This was done under reverse bending fatigue load with a load ratio of $R = -1$, a condition relevant to aeronautic structures. Residual stresses were measured using the X-ray diffraction method, and no post-weld treatment was applied. The results revealed that the base material had an endurance limit of 37% of the yield strength. The welding process reduced this endurance limit to 32%. Interestingly, the first instance of rewelding did not further decrease the endurance limit. However, the second instance of rewelding reduced the endurance limit to 20% of the yield strength. This suggests that while the first rewelding can extend the fatigue life by 100%, a second rewelding repair is not advisable when ensuring safety is paramount.

Sarmast et al. [28] undertook both empirical and computational studies to assess the effects of multi-pass repair welding on residual stress distributions in Gas Metal Arc (GMA)-welded T-joints of normal and high-strength structural steel. The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of this welding method for repairing fatigue-damaged welds. Initially, T-joint samples were welded, followed by the induction of cracks at the weld toes via cyclic loading. Depending on the crack length, these cracks were then machined on one or both sides of the plate. Each machined area underwent a two-pass welding restoration. Residual stresses, both longitudinal and transverse, were measured using the X-ray diffraction method. A finite element model, integrating thermometallurgical and mechanical features, was developed for each sample to analyse the residual stress distributions. Results suggest that repair welding increases the magnitude of residual stresses compared to the original weld, regardless of the

alloy or repair method. However, two-sided welding exhibited lower residual stress levels than one-sided welding, with this difference being more significant in higher-strength plates.

Schubnell et al. [29] evaluated the effect of a re-welding repair technique on the fatigue life of welded joints. They modelled the technique's application on a stiffener welded to a steel girder in highway and railway bridges. The study used an experimental approach, subjecting welded joint specimens to cyclic bending loads until cracks appeared. Afterward, the cracked areas were removed, and specimens were re-welded using the Gas Metal arc Welding (GMAW) method. The team employed non-destructive tests, like the Penetrant Testing (PT) method, to detect cracks. Specimens were made of both high-strength steel (S960QL) and low-strength steel (S355J2+N). S-N curves were presented for both original and repaired specimens. Comparatively, repaired specimens demonstrated a fatigue life at least equivalent to the original ones before cracking.

Fu et al. [30] evaluated the impact of rewelding as a fatigue repair technique on the fatigue life of rib-to-deck and diaphragm-to-rib welds in steel bridge decks under cyclic loading. Following the rewelding process, additional treatments were taken into account, such as polishing, heat treatment, and the application of Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) for strengthening purposes. The efficacy of post-welding procedures is also examined through the observation of the microstructure of the rewelded regions using a metallurgical microscope. Fatigue crack progression during testing cycles was charted for different specimens. The findings indicate that the process of rewelding has a positive impact on enhancing the fatigue life. The application of polishing and heat treatment techniques does not yield a substantial enhancement in the fatigue life subsequent to a rewelding repair. However, the implementation of CFRP strengthening subsequent to the rewelding repair process has been observed to result in a significant enhancement in power, with an increase of 3.75 times. The findings indicate that the optimal timing for rewelding is recommended to occur during the intermediate phase of crack propagation.

3.2.3. Fatigue repair via circular-arc cutout

The stress concentration at weld tips can be effectively reduced through semi-circular notching in adjacent to the welding in order to redistribute the internal stresses and transfer the high stresses to the semicircular arc with higher fatigue resistance. This method is successfully applied on vertical stiffeners of orthotropic steel deck bridge after detecting fatigue cracks [31]. Sakagami et al. [32] also verified the effectiveness of this repairing method using the results of Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) in addition to strain gauges and numerical simulations.

3.2.4. Fatigue repair via ultrasonic impact treatment

Ultrasonic Impact Treatment (UIT) or Ultrasonic Peening (UP) has been shown to be the most effective technique for fatigue performance improvement of welded elements compared to other methods such as hammer peening, grinding and TIG-dressing. Kudryavstev et al. [33] experimentally showed that this method can be successfully applied for repair and rehabilitation of the existing structures. The specimens rehabilitated after 50% of expected fatigue life with UP treatment showed

the similar results as the specimens were had initially treated. The treated specimens showed 5 to 10 times more fatigue life compared to specimens in the as-welded condition. Kudryavtsev et al. [34] studied different type of fatigue crack repairing and concluded that welding with ultrasonic peening result in longest fatigue life.

UIT has been successfully demonstrated as an effective method for enhancing the fatigue performance of repair welds in crane runway girders [35]. Notably, UIT is not only more efficient in terms of application speed compared to other methods like grinding, but it also significantly improves the fatigue life of welded plate girders. The study found that UIT increased the fatigue life of both original and repair welds approximately 8 times compared to their as-welded conditions. This underscores the potential of UIT as a powerful tool for fatigue life improvement in welded structures.

Kudryavtsev and Kleiman [36] present and analyse the outcomes of three sets of fatigue tests conducted on welded components in their original as-welded state, as well as subsequent to the implementation of UP treatment. The efficacy and cost-effectiveness of UP as a technique for enhancing the fatigue strength of welded components in materials with varying strengths has been demonstrated. The results suggest that UP application improve fatigue strength in welded components. UP has proven instrumental in increasing the fatigue life of welded elements during manufacturing, rehabilitation, and repairs. The UP technique has been widely adopted across sectors such as shipbuilding, bridge infrastructure, construction equipment, mining, automotive, and aerospace. Compared to alternative repair approaches like TIG-dressing and the use of LTT electrodes, UP proves to be the most effective.

3.2.5. Fatigue repair via hammer peening

Hammer peening is a surface modification method aimed at improving the fatigue performance of welded structures [37]. As a post-weld treatment, it induces surface compressive residual stresses, akin to those produced by shot peening and roller peening [38].

Branko et al. [39] conducted a detailed investigation into the fatigue performance of non-load carrying T-joints subjected to Three-Point Bending (3PB) loading. Their research was centred on assessing the effectiveness of the hammer peening technique in repairing cracked joints. The objective was to determine the fatigue life of joints with weld toe cracks that had undergone the hammer peening process. To achieve this, gain factors, denoted as g , were determined. The fatigue lives of the as-welded joints with fatigue cracks, which were marked and subsequently repaired through hammer peening, were observed to be notably higher compared to the fatigue lives of the original as-welded specimens. The study revealed that the positive impacts of repair were more pronounced in small fatigue cracks that had depths measuring less than 2.5 mm. X-ray diffraction was used to get values close to the yield stress in compression at the weld toe region in hammer-peened specimens, which is the main reason fatigue life is much increased.

Kirkhope et al. [40] undertook an experimental analysis to assess the effectiveness of three fatigue weld crack repair methods – hammer peening, burr grinding, and TIG dressing – in extending the fatigue life of welded ship components. Additionally, the study evaluated the real-world application of these

techniques on a typical ship structure detail, using the findings to formulate cost estimation factors. It also addresses the extent to which fatigue strength or life improvement can be attained, considerations related to corrosion protection, and the identification of optimal procedures. A series of experiments were conducted to apply the three techniques under similar conditions, aiming to correlate the methods with pertinent shipyard production standards. The installation efficiency for burr grinding and hammer peening clearly surpasses that of TIG dressing. In terms of costs, burr grinding emerged as the most economical, followed by TIG dressing, with hammer peening being the most expensive. The application of toe grinding, TIG dressing, and hammer peening techniques results in a notable enhancement of approximately 120%, 120%, and 300% in fatigue life, as evidenced by the S-N curve.

3.2.6. Fatigue repair via FRP strips or patches

Repairing fatigue damaged structures with FRP have a few advantages over other common methods such as high strength-to-weight ratio which makes it appropriate for aerospace industry to prolong the operational life of aged airplanes [41]. FRPs also have good resistance to corrosion and do not introduce new fatigue prone zones [42] with good potential use in bridge [43] and ship structures [44].

In 1987, Allan et al. [45], investigated the possible application of CFRP patches for repairing cracks in aluminium structural elements of ships and compared it with steel patch attached to aluminium plate using adhesive epoxies. The results suggest that proper fatigue performance of repaired elements with CFRP really depends on the proper technique of repairing. For instance, the specimen with fresh silane had the lifespan 3 to 10 times of the butt weld and similar the specimens with bonded steel patches. This repair can be successfully applied without initial weld repair as welding is challenging on aluminium elements on board.

Jie et al. [46] conducted a fatigue test on welded cruciform joints under tensile fatigue loading repaired by CFRP patches. The artificial cracks with depth of 1, 2 and 3 mm were created in specimens to simulate the effect of crack and then the specimen were repaired using 3 different types CFRP patches. The fatigue life determined once the fatigue crack reached half of the plate thickness. Irrespective of type of CFRP patch, using CFRP increased the fatigue life of specimens by a factor of two.

Nakamura et al. [47] also evaluate the effectiveness of CFRP repair on welded gusset plates. The specimen was loaded using four-point bending, creating uniform tensile stress ins specimens, and then repaired once the length of crack reached to 15 mm. The specimen with multi layered CFRP strips in addition to drill holes showed 80 times more fatigue life in comparison to the specimen without repair.

Chen et al. [48] also studied the performance of repaired rectangular hollow sections steel beams under fatigue tensile loading. The initial damage was created artificially by wire electrical discharge machining. The specimens were repaired subsequently using pre-stressed and non-prestressed CFRP plates. The results suggest outstanding extension of fatigue life in comparison to unrepaired specimens. The specimens strengthened by pre-stressed CFRP showed a fatigue life up to 35 times more than unrepaired specimens.

May et al. [49] studied the rate of fatigue crack growth in welded steel details repaired with Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP). The research included different specimen types, such as cruciform sections and longitudinally stiffened plates. They tested both plain steel specimens without any patches and those repaired with CFRP to improve fatigue life. Using CFRP patches was shown to increase lifespan by an estimated 50%. The study highlighted the strength and durability of the adhesive bond in specimens repaired with patches. The results from the tests were used to check the accuracy of FE models, which were then used to predict crack growth in both plain and repaired steel plates. The FE results demonstrate a strong correlation with the experimental results in accurately predicting the occurrence and length of cracks.

Chen et al. [50] evaluated the performance of CFRP sheet patching on steel plates with central cracks under varied axial fatigue loads at different angles. The plates, 500 mm long, 90 mm wide, and 8 mm thick, had intentional notches creating cracks of 27 mm, 36 mm, and 45 mm. High-modulus carbon fibre and epoxy adhesive Araldite 420 were used for repairs. When subjected to loads at angles of 0°, 15°, and 30°, specimens with a 45 mm initial crack saw fatigue life increases of 418%, 352%, and 158%, respectively. Moreover, repair efficiency was higher for longer cracks, with efficiencies of 278%, 337%, and 350% for the respective crack lengths.

3.2.7. Fatigue repair via short repair (crack removal)

Rodriguez-Sanchez et al. [51] evaluated the effectiveness of crack removal technique in butt-welded joints with full-penetration as-welded welding for fatigue life extension of offshore structures. The cracks ground out using disk cutting and crack depth growth monitored through Alternating current potential difference (ACPD) technique. The results based on limited test programs shows that if the fatigue crack is removed when the crack penetrated up to 30% of plate thickness, the fatigue life can be extended by a factor of two.

The other study [52] shows that wet welding the resulted groove after removal of the crack can increase the fatigue life by a factor of 2 to 3. This study suggests that filling up the resulted groove with welding shows better fatigue performance compared to empty groove case.

3.2.8. Fatigue repair via drill holes (stop-holes)

The singularity at crack tips can be removed using stop drilling. It is crucial to remove the crack tip completely to avoid unexpected results. However, locating the fatigue crack tip during in-situ drilling can be challenging, and drilling slightly behind the tip can cause the crack to behave like a short crack growing out of a notch. This can lead to abnormally high growth rates, making the outcome unpredictable. Therefore, exercising caution and precision during drilling or grinding is essential to ensure complete crack tip removal [53]. Nakamura et al. [47] examined this method for repairing welded web gusset joint under fatigue loading. The result showed 1.6 times improvement in the lifespan of the specimen without repair.

Xie et al. [54] conducted a study combining experimental and finite element methods to assess fatigue cracks in steel box girders. Specimens, replicating deck and U-rib welded components, were created using CO₂ protected welding. Cracks of varied dimensions were introduced via Wire Electrical Discharge Machining (WEDM). The study emphasized the use of an inclined hole as a preventive measure against crack propagation. Finite element analysis indicated that this inclined hole reduced stress concentration by 27% compared to a traditional vertical hole and offered superior stress distribution.

3.2.9. Other fatigue repair methods

Vilhauer et al. [55] evaluated the effectiveness of the post installation of tension bolts on coverplates to enhance fatigue life of steel bridge girders. The method applied individually and in combination of Ultrasonic Impact Treatment method. The results showed that post installing of tensioned bolts could not prolong the fatigue crack initiation of the specimens.

The potential use of self-healing material for Al-ally for aerospace application is evaluated by Fisher et al. [56] and showed 90% strength recover under tensile loading.

It is recognized that a tensile overload can result in the retardation of fatigue crack growth [53]. Plasticity-induced crack closure has been identified as the main mechanism behind the retardation of crack growth due to overload. The residual plastic deformation leaves extra material on the flanks of the crack, which results in an early closure of the crack and subsequently reduces the effective force driving the crack [57].

The application of an overload carries the risk of fracturing the already cracked structure, making it an unsuitable approach for fatigue crack repair techniques. It appears that the introduction of foreign materials into the crack flanks could potentially serve a similar purpose in retarding crack growth [58]. Artificial crack closure, achieved by introducing foreign materials like aluminium powder or epoxy resin, can extend the fatigue life of structures [53]. Additionally, these materials serve a sealing function by filling pores and cracks, which is particularly beneficial for specialized structures such as vacuum chambers.

3.2.10. Fatigue repair methods effectiveness

To offer a comprehensive overview of the effectiveness of the reviewed fatigue repair methods, the results of 25 scientific articles have been summarized in Table 1. The second column indicates the potential application of each repair method. This could relate to specific structural details relevant to a given industry or it might highlight potential applications within an industry as suggested by the authors. Additionally, the application might address the impact of a particular repair method on a specific material type. It is important to note that the effectiveness is determined by comparing the remaining fatigue life of a repaired specimen to that of an unrepaired one, unless otherwise specified in the table.

Table 1 – Effectiveness of fatigue repair methods

No.	Source	Application	Repair method	Effectiveness
1	[39]	Medium strength structural steel	Hammer peening	Independent of the presence of fatigue cracks
2	[23]	Railway	Welding	Not discuss quantitatively
3	[47]	Bridge welded web and gusset joints	CFRP and drill-holes	1.6 times for drilled hole and 80 times for multi-layered CFRP with drilled holes
4	[46]	CFRP repair of welded steel	CFRP patch	2 times
5	[51]	Offshore structure	Crack removal using disk cutting	2 times
6	[25]	High strength low ally - weld	Weld Repaired crack	-
7	[52]	Offshore structure	Crack removal and subsequent welding the groove	2 to 3 times
8	[35]	Crane runway girder	Ultrasonic impact treatment	8 times
9	[33]	Steel bridge and welded plates	Ultrasonic peening	5 to 10 times
10	[18]	High strength steel - weld	Welding	-
11	[26]	Orthotropic steel deck bridge	Adding opposite side fillet weld	5 to 8 times
12	[36]	Bridges	Ultrasonic peening	1.5 times
13	[54]	Steel Box Girder	Inclined stop hole	Inclined holes reduce maximum stress by 27 compared to normal hole
14	[56]	Aluminium alloys in aerospace	SMA Self-healing materials	90% strength recovery for tensile strength
15	[45]	CFRP repair of aluminium ships	CFRP and steel patch using adhesive epoxy	3 to 10 times
16	[28]	Structural steel T-joints	Multi-pass repair welding	Repairing in one or two sides, the repair welding increases the magnitude of the residual stresses compared to the initial weld
17	[29]	High and low strength steel	Material removal and re-welding	Repaired specimen in both high and low strength steel have at least the fatigue life as original specimen
18	[27]	Aerospace	Rewelding	2 times
19	[53]	Pipes	Infiltrating epoxy resin and alumina powder	30000 to 60000 extra cycles
20	[48]	Hollow sections (in bridge and offshore structures)	Prestressed CFRP plate	7 to 35 times compared for prestressed specimens and 3 to 14 for not prestressed specimens

21	[59]	Steel bridges with orthotropic decks	Bonded steel patches for crack repair	-
22	[19]	Offshore structures	Surface repairs (short repair) crack removal	-
23	[40]	Ship structures	TIG- hammer peening	TIG 2.2 times and hammer peening 4.0 times
24	[50]	FRP repairing under mix mode fatigue cracking	CFRP sheets	5.18, 4.52 and 2.58 with load application angles of 0°, 15° and 30° for 45mm crack length 3.78, 4.37 and 4.52 initial crack lengths of 27 mm, 36 mm and 45 mm for 15° load
25	[30]	Steel Bridge Deck Welds	Rewelding with and without polishing, heat treatment, and strengthening with CFRP	Rewelding 2 times and CFRP strengthening after rewelding increased cycles by 275% (3.75 times).

4. Material and Methods

In this section, the methodologies employed for stress and fatigue analysis of the entry/exit vacuum chamber are presented. Discussion encompasses the 3D modelling of the chamber and the utilization of its scalable feature. Extensive details on FE modelling, including shell modelling, boundary conditions, and connections, are provided. Furthermore, methods for stress calculation in fatigue analysis, specifically within the realms of the structural hot spot and fracture mechanics methods, are elaborated upon. Sub-modelling technique is proposed as a targeted approach for FE simulation of large vacuum chambers, aiming to manage the computational demand required in fatigue analysis.

4.1. Scalable 3D modelling of the vacuum chamber

A 3D model of the chamber is constructed using existing 2D CAD files, in-situ measurements, visits, and an inventory list of the chamber that includes components purchased for chamber construction. The 3D model shown in Figure 1 is modelled in Autodesk Inventor® software. Considering the primary objective of this modelling is to facilitate its transfer for FE analysis, minor mechanical details and components with negligible structural impact are not included in this model. The geometric representation of the model encompasses hydraulic jacks, the chamber lid, and the chamber body.

Figure 1 – ISO view of 3D model of the vacuum chamber

Section views of the chamber are displayed in Figure 2 to provide a more comprehensive understanding of its inner components that influence its structural behaviour. The slim openings on both sides of the chamber serve as transportation portals and are closed via a mechanical shutter during pump down.

Although the rollers responsible for glass transportation, installed on the chamber's lower plate, are not explicitly modelled, their weight is incorporated into the FE analysis.

Figure 2 – Different sections of the vacuum chambers

The 3D model under discussion is parametrized to be scalable. It is primarily characterized by two independent parameters: width and length. These parameters represent the dimensions of the glass pane that can be accommodated within the chamber. All other dimensions of the chamber are contingent upon these two parameters, effectively making them a reflection of the glass pane's size. Consequently, any alterations to the dimensions of the glass pane will automatically trigger corresponding changes in the chamber's dimensions.

The importance of this parametrization lies in its adaptability to various plant requirements, as different facilities utilize vacuum chambers or glass panes of varying sizes. This scalable 3D model eliminates the need to create new 3D models from scratch for each size of the vacuum chamber, thereby enhancing efficiency. The primary parameters can be accessed in Autodesk Inventor® by navigating to the "Manage" tab and selecting the "Parameters" icon. Modifications to these parameters can be made under the "Equation" column for "User Parameters", as highlighted in red in Figure 3.

Parameters

Parameter Name	Consumed by	Unit/Type	Equation	Nominal Value	Tolerance	Value	...	...	...
d375	Sketch39	mm	375 mm	375.000000	<Default>	0.000000			
d376	SmallGlassOpening	mm	Length + 600 mm	6600.000000	<Default>	0.000000			
d377	SmallGlassOpening	deg	0.00 deg	0.000000	<Default>	0.000000			
d379	Sketch40	mm	320 mm	320.000000	<Default>	320.000000			
d381	Sketch40	mm	320 mm	320.000000	<Default>	320.000000			
d382	Sketch40	mm	50 mm	50.000000	<Default>	50.000000			
d407	Sketch40	mm	Width + 730 mm	2730.000000	<Default>	2730.000000			
d408	Sketch40	mm	130.000 mm	130.000000	<Default>	130.000000			
Reference Parameters									
d16		mm	100.000 mm	100.000000	<Default>	100.000000			
d119		mm	170.000 mm	170.000000	<Default>	170.000000			
d169		mm	130.000 mm	130.000000	<Default>	130.000000			
d176		deg	180.00 deg	180.000000	<Default>	180.000000			
d179		mm	650.000 mm	650.000000	<Default>	650.000000			
d250		mm	40.000 mm	40.000000	<Default>	40.000000			
d258		mm	40.000 mm	40.000000	<Default>	40.000000			
d313		mm	220.000 mm	220.000000	<Default>	220.000000			
d315		mm	3190.000 mm	3190.000000	<Default>	3190.000000			
User Parameters									
Width	d407, d370, d326, d328, d3...	mm	3300	2000.000000		2000.000000			☒
Length	d376, d365, d281, d214, d1...	mm	6000	6000.000000		6000.000000			☒
Embedding 1									

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 Link | Immediate Update | Export to XML

Figure 3 – Parametrization of dimensions for a scalable 3D model

The parameters labelled as "Length" and "Width" offer a high degree of flexibility in the model, as they can be modified either collectively or independently, depending on the specific requirements. This allows for a wide range of dimensional configurations for the vacuum chamber. For instance, Figure 4 illustrates how the width of the chamber can be adjusted, demonstrating the model's adaptability to accommodate different sizes.

Figure 4 – Demonstrating the adjustable width of the vacuum chamber in the scalable model

4.2. Preparation of the 3D model for FE analysis

The 3D model, initially created in Autodesk Inventor®, was exported as a STEP file to ANSYS® SpaceClaim [14]. This transition was necessary to preprocess the model geometrically for the subsequent FE analysis. During this preprocessing stage, particular attention was given to the

connections between components. These were meticulously controlled to avoid any disconnected regions, self-intersections, or over-connections, ensuring the model's integrity.

In the next phase, surface bodies and solid elements were clearly defined, and their interconnections were established. This step is crucial as it sets the foundation for the FE analysis by determining how different parts of the model interact with each other. Figure 5 provides a visual representation of the imported 3D model, showcasing the results of the preprocessing steps for the FE analysis.

Figure 5 – 3D Model Imported into ANSYS® SpaceClaim [14]

To reduce computational effort, steel plates with a length-to-thickness ratio greater than 20 were modelled as surface bodies. These surface bodies are modelled using shell elements with nodes possessing six degrees of freedom, comprising three rotational and three translational degrees of freedom. This allows for the simulation of both membrane and bending behaviours. The components that were converted into surface bodies through mid-surface extraction are depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Surface bodies for shell analysis

Components with intricate geometries, such as hydraulic jack brackets, as well as thick components like base plates, are represented as solid bodies in the modelling process. These solid bodies, as illustrated in Figure 7, are meshed using solid elements for FE analysis.

Figure 7 – Solid bodies

Figure 8 presents the positioning of surface and solid bodies within the vacuum chamber. At this stage, a gap emerges between the solid and surface bodies due to the mid-surface extraction process. This discontinuity will be subsequently addressed in ANSYS Workbench [15] by establishing bonded boundary connections between the surface and solid bodies.

Figure 8 – Illustration of surface bodies (blue) and Solid bodies (red)

As depicted in Figure 9, the surface bodies are connected using shared topology. The free edges are marked in red, while the connections between two and three plates are designated by blue and pink colours, respectively. This shared topology effectively links the finite elements of the various steel plates together, thereby simulating the weld connection between the plates. However, it is important to note that this method does not account for local effects such as intermittent welding or the specific geometry of the weld seam. To study these effects, shell-to-solid sub-modelling (refer to Figure 23) can be employed. This method, which utilizes solid elements and is grounded in fracture mechanics [60] or notch stress [61], allows for the consideration of such intricate details.

Figure 9 – Illustration of interconnected surface bodies via shared topology

4.3. FE modelling

The Finite Element modelling is executed using ANSYS® Mechanical [15] software, with the refined geometry imported from ANSYS® SpaceClaim [14]. A static structural analysis (an implicit solver) is employed for the simulation of the model, an approach that is well-suited for static and quasi-static problems. This method is particularly appropriate for structures subjected to loading conditions that do not generate substantial inertia and damping effects [62]. Given the limited displacement and stress levels under atmospheric loading, non-linearities such as plasticity and large deflection are disregarded during the analysis. However, interaction-based non-linearity, such as frictional contact, is considered.

4.3.1. Material

The vacuum chamber is constructed from ST 37-2 steel, which is characterized by Young's modulus of 200,000 MPa and the yield strength of 235 MPa. In the FE analysis of the chamber, the material is assumed to behave as perfectly elastic, with no plasticity defined. The fatigue characteristics of the material are determined based on the S-N curves proposed by IIW recommendations [5] for high-cycle applications.

The selection of the appropriate S-N curve for fatigue analysis can vary depending on the method used to calculate the stress field. This could be based on traditional nominal stress, the structural hot spot method [63], or the Notch Stress Intensity Factor (N-SIF) approach [64]. The primary reason underlying this variation lies in the distinct techniques each method utilizes to compute the stress range.

For instance, the nominal stress method involves the consideration of the mean stress in the section, whereas the hot spot method determines the value of stress concentration via FE analysis. These stress

magnitudes, produced by each method, are then statistically fit to the experimental fatigue data, resulting in distinct S-N curves or FAT classes. In the case of the hot spot method, FAT classes 90 and 100 are designated for the fatigue analysis of welded components, whilst FAT 160 is utilized for non-welded parts. These classifications are illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – S-N curves for steel's fatigue resistance in very high cycle applications, based on IIW recommendations [5]

4.3.2. Boundary conditions

4.3.2.1. Supports (Vacuum Chamber legs)

The vacuum chambers are mounted on four wheels, enabling unrestricted movement along a rail in the z-direction, as depicted in Figure 11. While the wheels themselves are not explicitly modelled, their physical interactions are implicitly simulated through the use of "remote displacement". Remote points are defined at the connection of the wheel to the rail, and this point is constrained to the surface of the support, as it is shown in Figure 11. Although the translational movement is restricted in the x and y directions, the chamber is able to move freely along the z-axis.

Figure 11 – Modelling of vacuum chamber supports

4.3.2.2. Connection with the next chamber

The entry/exit vacuum chamber is connected to the next (buffer) chamber using 26 M16×110 mm bolts of grade 8.8. While the bolts themselves are not explicitly modelled in this simulation, their presence is inferred through the creation of bolt holes. Around each bolt hole, a circle with a 12 mm radius is drawn to form a ring. These rings, imprinted at the locations where the bolt heads rest on the endplate, are defined as fixed supports, thus establishing a connection to the adjacent chamber. Figure 12 shows the modelled connection between the entry/exit and buffer vacuum chambers.

Figure 12 – Modelling of the connection between entry/exit and buffer vacuum chambers

4.3.2.3. Gravity Loading

This simulation incorporates certain assumptions to ensure a reasonably accurate representation of the real-world scenario while maintaining computational efficiency. One such assumption relates to the weight of the mechanical and manufacturing equipment, including transport rollers, that the vacuum chamber needs to accommodate. The estimated weight of this equipment is around 2000 kilograms, and it is applied to the bottom plate of the chamber using a designated remote point, as depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13 – Application of gravity load on the bottom plate of the vacuum chamber

The self-weight of the chamber components is taken into account by utilizing the density of steel, which is set at 7850 kg/m³. Using this density and the volume of each component, ANSYS® Mechanical [15] calculates their respective weights and incorporates them in the gravity analysis.

Maintaining the weight of the chamber lid within specific limits is crucial to ensure that the hydraulic jack can effectively lift it during maintenance periods, as depicted in Figure 14. By controlling the weight, the lid can be safely and efficiently lifted when necessary. Based on the original design, the calculated weight of the lid amounts to 9363 kg.

Figure 14 – Entry/exit vacuum chamber lid

The weight of the chamber body, excluding any connected mechanical parts such as the hydraulic jack (refer to Figure 15), is measured at 11028 kg. This weight represents the standalone mass of the chamber body, providing a reference for assessing its structural requirements and handling considerations.

Figure 15 – Self-weight of chamber body

4.3.2.4. Atmospheric pressure

Upon the insertion of the glass pane into the entry vacuum chamber, the pressure within the chamber is reduced from atmospheric pressure to an intermediate vacuum level using vacuum pumps. Subsequently, after the transportation of the glass from the entry chamber into the buffer chamber, the pressure inside the chamber returns to atmospheric pressure. This creates a cyclic loading pattern with constant frequency and magnitude.

To simulate the interaction between the vacuum chamber and the atmospheric pressure, a pressure equivalent to 1 bar (atmospheric pressure) is applied to all surfaces of the vacuum chamber that come into contact with the low-pressure environment. This pressure distribution is depicted in Figure 16.

B: Static Structural Bascharge Plant

Pressure on body

Time: 1. s

- A** Pressure on Lid: 0.1 MPa
- B** Pressure on body: 0.1 MPa

Figure 16 – Application of atmospheric pressure on the vacuum chamber

4.3.3. Interactions

As mentioned earlier, the steel plates within the chamber are interconnected using shared topology, and the weld seams are not explicitly modelled in the global model. While the structurally significant components of the hydraulic jacks, such as the hydraulic jack brackets, are explicitly modelled, the mechanical parts are defined using joints and springs. The connection between the chamber lid and the body is also modelled using a frictional contact.

4.3.3.1. Hydraulic jacks

Hydraulic jacks, which are essential for the opening of the chamber lid during routine maintenance and overhauls, consist of two primary components: the upper bracket (or movable part) and the bottom bracket (or fixed part). The interaction between the upper and lower brackets is modelled using joints and springs.

The upper bracket pivots within the socket, as indicated by the green circle in Figure 17, into the fixed part to lift the lid. To simulate this behaviour, a “*revolute joint*”¹ is defined between the internal surfaces of the sockets. This joint is implemented to rotate freely along the Z-axis while constraining all other degrees of freedom.

¹ A pre-configured joint type in the ANSYS® Mechanical software

Figure 17 – Simulation of the revolute joints in the hydraulic jack: an implicit approach

The hydraulic pressure is exerted via a rod, as indicated by the green rounded rectangle in Figure 18. This rod is engaged during cyclic atmospheric pressure, resulting in a constraint in its axial direction. To implicitly simulate the behaviour of the hydraulic jack rod, a longitudinal spring, reflecting the axial stiffness of the rod, is modelled. This spring is then connected to the internal face of the upper bracket's sockets, thereby providing a realistic representation of the hydraulic jack rod's manoeuvre during plant operation. This modelling technique reduces computational demands and eliminates the need for modelling the mechanical components involved.

Figure 18 – Implicit simulation of the hydraulic jacks rod

4.3.3.2. Contacts

The interaction between the chamber lid and the body is represented as frictional contact in the model, with an assumed friction coefficient of 0.2, as depicted in Figure 19. The friction coefficients for contact surfaces between steel components can vary significantly, influenced by a range of factors. These include conditions such as the presence of lubricants, the degree of surface rusting, and the type of coating applied to the steel [65]. It is important to note that no additional experiments were conducted to ascertain the precise value of the friction coefficient.

Figure 19 – Frictional contact between chamber lid and body

As a result of mid-surface extraction, a gap emerges between the surface and solid bodies, equivalent to half the thickness of the steel plates. This gap, while a natural outcome of the extraction process, presents a potential issue in terms of maintaining the structural integrity of the assembly. In order to prevent any potential displacement between the solid and surface bodies, a bonded connection¹ with Multi-Point Constrained (MPC) formulation is established between them. The bonded connections surface and solid bodies are shown in Figure 20.

¹ In terms of Abaqus terminology, this 'bonded connection' can be considered equivalent to a 'tie constraint', which serves a similar purpose of preventing relative movement between two entities in the model.

Contact Region 38
Items: 10 of 34 indicated
5/16/2023 11:41 AM

- A Contact Region (Contact Bodies)
- B Contact Region (Target Bodies)
- C Contact Region 2 (Contact Bodies)
- D Contact Region 2 (Target Bodies)
- E Contact Region 3 (Contact Bodies)
- F Contact Region 3 (Target Bodies)
- G Contact Region 4 (Contact Bodies)
- H Contact Region 4 (Target Bodies)
- I Contact Region 5 (Contact Bodies)
- J Contact Region 5 (Target Bodies)

Figure 20 – Bonded contacts between shell and solid bodies

4.3.4. Computational Mesh

The vacuum chamber's global model is meshed using a total of 123,000 elements and 118,000 nodes, as it is illustrated in Figure 21. This includes 25,000 tetrahedron and 20,000 hexahedron elements, along with 67,000 quadrilateral shell elements. The remaining elements are comprised of wedges, pyramids in solid bodies, and triangles in surface bodies.

The surface bodies within the model are meshed using 50-mm linear quadrilateral shell elements known as 'Quad4'. Each of these elements possesses six degrees of freedom - three rotational and three translational - enabling them to consider both membrane and bending behaviour.

The surface bodies are meshed using the 'Shell181' element type. This element type is particularly suitable for modelling thin to moderately-thick shell components. It is formulated according to the first-order shear-deformation theory, also referred to as the Mindlin-Reissner shell theory [66].

Considering the application of implicit analysis, it is important to note that this form of analysis does not incorporate degrees of freedom for either accelerations or velocities. In this context, the 'Shell181' element within the ANSYS® computational framework exhibits suitability for applications involving linear analysis, large rotation, and/or extensive strain nonlinearity. This element also accounts for changes in shell thickness during nonlinear analyses [62].

The solid components are primarily meshed using 4-node Tetrahedrons and 8-node Hexahedrons solid elements, which are applied to supports and hydraulic jack brackets, respectively. The mesh size is set at 25 mm for the hydraulic jack brackets and 10 mm for the supports and base plates.

The solid bodies in the model are meshed using the "SOLID185" element type. This element type is defined by eight nodes, with each node having three degrees of freedom in translation. The "SOLID185" element type is capable of adapting to form prisms, tetrahedrons, and pyramids when dealing with irregular regions [62].

Figure 21 – Meshing details on the vacuum chamber

4.4. Fatigue analysis

The stress-life (S-N) methodology [67] is considered for the fatigue analysis of the vacuum chamber under atmospheric cyclic loading with constant amplitude. Contrary to the strain-life (ϵ -N) approach, which is apt for low-cycle fatigue scenarios [68], the stress-life method does not consider material plasticity. Nevertheless, for the high-cycle fatigue range, where the material remains within the elastic zone, the stress-life method provides reasonably accurate predictions.

The fatigue analysis conducted does not account for any potential impact of corrosion. It is presumed that the material's behaviour is entirely elastic, devoid of any pre-existing fatigue damage. Moreover, any influence that the initiation of fatigue cracks might exert on the subsequent development of cracks elsewhere within the chamber is disregarded.

The International Institute of Welding (IIW) [5] has outlined four methods for stress evaluation in fatigue design, namely, nominal stress, structural hot spot stress, effective notch stress, and Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM). Due to the complex geometry of the vacuum chamber, the nominal stress method is not applicable. For steel-plated structures, the conventional approach is the hot spot method, which provides satisfactory accuracy and is reasonably efficient in terms of finite element (FE) modelling time.

The structural hot spot method is more efficient than the effective notch stress and LEFM methods for large models because it allows for the use of shell modelling techniques in stress field calculation with reasonably fine elements [69]. In contrast, effective notch stress and LEFM methods normally require detailed-solid FE models with very fine mesh for the calculation of the stress intensity factor [70].

However, the structural hot spot method it has limitations in considering fatigue crack initiation from the weld root [4] and in modelling the progression of crack growth. In contrast, LEFM methods provide

strategies for predicting crack propagation and estimating the remaining lifespan of structures that have suffered fatigue damage [71].

Researchers have recently devised FE-based methodologies aimed at providing rapid fatigue analysis, which is predicated on the local stress state. [72]; for instance, Peak Stress Method (PSM) has been developed to provide fast fatigue assessment of welded structures with complex geometry, employing coarse meshes to reduce computational demand [73].

4.4.1. Structural hot spot method

Unlike the nominal stress method, in the structural hot spot method is possible to directly consider stress concentration in fatigue analysis using the result of FE analysis. However, the structural hot-spot stress is calculated through extrapolation from previously referenced points with a specific distance from hot spots such as stiffener end or weld toe [69]. Various methodologies have been proposed for the computation of stress in hot spots, including Linear Surface Extrapolation (LSE), Through Thickness Stress Determination (TTSD), and the Dong method. For two-dimensional structural details, these methods exhibit a fair level of precision. [74]. In the present study, the LSE method is employed, with extrapolation points situated at distances of $0.4t$ and $1.0t$ from the intersections of the plates. This is conducted in accordance with Eq. (1)

$$\sigma_{hs} = 1.67 \times \sigma_{0.4t} - 0.67 \sigma_{1.0t} \quad (1)$$

Where “ t ” represents the thickness of the plate, and “ σ_{hs} ” denotes the stress at a hot spot. “ $\sigma_{0.4t}$ ” and “ $\sigma_{1.0t}$ ” are calculated as nodal stress by generating meshes at $0.4t$ and $1.0t$, respectively, using virtual topology. This process is illustrated in Figure 22.

Figure 22 – Linear surface extrapolation for calculating hot spot stress

4.4.2. Fatigue strength modifications

4.4.2.1. Stress mean effect

According to IIW [5] and EN 1993-1-9 [4], an enhancement factor can be applied to increase the fatigue strength of unwelded components or stress-relieved welded parts under compressive force. This enhancement can be achieved using a simplified method that considers just 60% of the compressive stress, resulting in a diminished stress range. As the welded details in the vacuum chamber have not undergone stress relief, the enhancement derived from the stress ratio effect is applied exclusively to unwelded components under compressive stress. During the pump-down process, the flanges of the channels (chamber ribs) are subject to compression. Consequently, only 60% of the stress experienced by the flanges is taken into account.

It is worth noting that more sophisticated theories on the effect of mean stress exist in the literature for fatigue analysis. These include but are not limited to, the Goodman, Soderberg, and Gerber correction theories [75], which are among the most recognized. However, as these methods have not been fully implemented by fatigue codes, a simpler and more conservative approach is adopted for considering the mean stress effect, as previously discussed.

4.4.2.2. Wall thickness effect

A thickness reduction factor, denoted as $f(t)$, is applied in accordance with the IIW [5] recommendations for plates exceeding a thickness of 25 mm. With the exception of the ribs and endplates attached to them, all other plates, inclusive of the hydraulic jacks brackets, have a thickness exceeding 25 mm, with some plates reaching up to 80 mm in thickness. The calculation of the thickness reduction factor is conducted using Eq. (2).

$$f(t) = \left(\frac{t_{ref}}{t_{eff}} \right)^n \quad (2)$$

Where “ t_{ref} ” is equal to 25 mm and “ n ” is equal to 0.3 for cruciform joints with as-welded conditions. The “ t_{eff} ” denotes the effective thickness, which is equal to the plate thickness if the ratio of the weld toe distance to the thickness is less than 2 according to IIW recommendations [5]. Finally, $f(t)$ is multiplied by the FAT class of the structural detail.

4.5. Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics

Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) is based on analysing cracks in linear elastic materials. This methodology offers an instrumental framework for addressing a vast array of practical challenges in engineering, including the safety evaluation and remaining life estimation of cracked components [76]. The LEFM approach fundamentally relies on the stress intensity factor [77], which represents the stress state close to the crack tip or notch. This metric is a function of the applied stress, the crack size, and the geometry of the component [78].

Fracture mechanics is employed to predict crack propagation only after the crack has initially formed or nucleated.; therefore, it is not suitable for predicting crack initiation [52]. Nonetheless, real-world materials and structural elements are not devoid of imperfections. They usually contain internal anomalies like pores and cavities or surface irregularities such as cracks and indentations [79]. For instance, weld seams are prone to a variety of flaws and material discontinuities, including cracks and crack-like defects such as incomplete penetration, hot and cold cracks and lack of fusion [80]. Considering half of the root gap in partially penetrated welds, or 0.1 mm as recommended by IIW [5] for initial crack size in weld root, the fatigue life can be computed utilizing the LEFM methodology through the integration of Paris' law [81]. This is represented in Eq. (3)

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \Delta K^m \quad (3)$$

In this equation, da/dN represents the rate of fatigue crack growth per load cycle. Here, " a " corresponds to the depth of the crack and " N " represents the number of cycles. The parameters " C " and " m " denote material constants, and ΔK is the range of the stress intensity factor.

In a study conducted in 1969 [82], which investigated steels with yield strengths ranging from 185 to 432 MPa, a specific relationship was proposed between the material constants and the yield stress of the steel.

$$m = 3.94 - 0.00379 f_y \quad (4)$$

$$\log_{10} C = 0.0107 f_y - 15.055 \quad (5)$$

In situations where weld fatigue cracks stem from internal defects, such as slag inclusions or inadequate root fusion, they may consistently evolve within the weld seam throughout their lifecycle. On the other hand, if a crack arises from the weld's toe, it advances from the weld seam to the Heat-Affected Zone (HAZ), eventually propagating into the base material [83]. Consequently, in this study, longitudinal fillet weld cracks are classified as weld root cracks.

Conversely, cracks that initiate from the weld toe and expand into the base material are classified as weld toe cracks. The IIW [5] provides specific material constant recommendations for crack growth in both weld toe cracks and root cracks, which are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 – Material constants [5]

Steel	Root cracks (weld metal)	Weld toes cracks (parent material)
C	5.21×10^{-13}	3.00×10^{-13}
m	3	3

In order to proceed with fracture mechanics analysis, having discussed the material constants in Paris's law, it becomes essential to calculate the Stress Intensity Factor (SIF). The application of LEFM has

led to the stress intensity concept to relate flaw size, component geometry, and fracture toughness [84]. The Stress Intensity Factor (SIF), often denoted as “K”, is a fundamental parameter in fracture mechanics. Its function is to predict the intensity of the stress field near the tip of a crack, which can result from a distant load or residual stresses. The SIF serves as a theoretical framework that enables us to predict not only the initiation but also the progression and directional course of crack propagation [85].

Closed-form solutions for the stress intensity factor have been developed for problems encompassing basic configurations. However, for more complex scenarios, “K” can be estimated using either experimental testing or numerical analysis methods [86]. Given the condition of an internal crack within an infinite plate subjected to remote tensile stress, it has been demonstrated [87] that the stress intensity factor of a through-thickness crack in the same plate under uniaxial loading can be represented by Eq. (6).

$$K = \sigma\sqrt{\pi a} \quad (6)$$

For a part-through crack or a crack in a semi-infinite body [88], a geometric correction factor [Y] can be incorporated into Eq. (6). This factor accounts for parameters such as the free surface at the mouth of the crack, the free surface ahead of the crack, and crack tip plasticity [89]. The modified equation is as follows:

$$K = Y\sigma\sqrt{\pi a} \quad (7)$$

The geometrical correction factor is 1.12 for edge crack in a semi-infinite body [88]. The geometrical correction factor derived from the ideal case can be found in the existing literature in the form closed-form solution. The numerical solutions and regression analyses for specific geometries under given loading can also be sourced from existing literature. These regression analyses typically account for factors such as a/c (crack aspect ratio) and a/T (crack depth), which can influence the stress intensity factor [90].

However, the entry/exit vacuum chambers present not only intricate geometries but also complex stress states. These combined factors make finding similar formulations for plated structures in existing literature nearly impossible. Therefore, a shell-to-solid sub-model of the critical welded components in the vacuum chamber has been developed for LEFM analysis using ANSYS® Mechanical [15]. Semi-elliptical cracks are introduced into this model, and stress intensity factors for the crack end and deepest points are computed.

As previously mentioned, sub-models derived from the global model are utilized for fatigue analysis. Shell-to-shell and shell-to-solid sub-modelling techniques are employed for structural hotspot and Linear LEFM methods, respectively. The use of solid models enables the modelling of weld seam profiles and semi-elliptical cracks, which is not feasible with shell models.

The geometric size of sub-models used for LEFM analysis is relatively smaller than those used for structural hotspot methods. This size difference is primarily due to two factors. Firstly, the fracture mechanics analysis requires a higher number of elements. Given the limitations of ANSYS® version 2022 R1 [15], meshing with hexahedral elements is not feasible for fracture mechanics, necessitating the use of tetrahedron elements instead. Additionally, the presence of a solid body and a crack significantly increases the number of required elements.

Secondly, the ANSYS® version 2022 R1 [15] does not support the simulation of a crack in a fracture mechanic module for a model including frictional contact. As a result, the welded plates in the chamber lid and body are analysed separately to circumvent the need for frictional contact.

Figure 23 illustrates the modelling of one of the longitudinal weld cracks. These cracks are categorized as weld root cracks due to their propagation exclusively within the weld seam rather than the parent material. A surface crack, with a depth of 1 mm, is generated at the location where crack initiation has occurred in the plant. The aspect ratio of the crack, represented as "a/c", is assumed to be 15, where "a" and "c" are the depth and length of the semi-elliptical crack, respectively. The largest contour radius is set at 2 mm. The semi-elliptical crack is meshed using the "Hex Dominant" method.

Figure 23 – Representation of a semi-elliptical crack modelled in ANSYS® [15]

4.5.1. Effect of welding residual stress on fatigue crack growth

In fatigue crack propagation analysis, the approach can either be numerical, as in the case of FE analysis, or analytical with methods such as influence coefficients or weight functions. Numerical methods necessitate accounting for the redistribution of residual stress due to crack propagation. In

contrast, analytical methods use the stress distribution across the uncracked section as their input [91]. In this context, while residual stresses do not influence the stress intensity factor range (ΔK), they affect the mean stress intensity factor (K) and the R-ratio. The respective equations are given as follows:

$$\Delta K = (K_{max} + K_r) - (K_{min} + K_r) = K_{max} - K_{min} \quad (8)$$

$$\bar{K} = 0.5 (K_{max} + K_{min}) + K_r \quad (9)$$

Where K_r and $\bar{K}$ represent the residual stress and mean stress intensity factor, respectively.

4.6. Sub-modelling technique

The need for a relatively fine element size becomes apparent when striving to pinpoint precisely the structural hot spots that are essential for fatigue analysis. However, the application of a fine mesh throughout the entire global model considerably amplifies computational requirements, making the process highly resource-demanding. To attain the necessary precision, techniques such as local mesh refinement [92] or the sub-modelling method [93] can be employed. However, the model's complexity can make local mesh refinement challenging. The mesh quality, especially in transition zones, may not necessarily improve, and the number of elements can remain notably high due to the size of the chamber.

The sub-modelling technique emerges as a practical solution to these challenges. The sub-modelling technique operates on the principle of Saint-Venant, which states that the stress distribution in regions distant from areas of stress concentration can be effectively represented by a corresponding set of equivalent displacements [9]. It enables focused analysis of problematic areas, modelled with a fine mesh, thereby providing a targeted approach. This method significantly alleviates computational demands, thereby optimizing efficiency while maintaining meticulous detail.

When employing the sub-modelling technique, if the boundaries of the sub-model are sufficiently distant from the areas of stress concentration, the sub-model can yield highly accurate results [62]. The established method of integrating the displacement field from the global model is consistently adopted within the sub-model. This incorporation of pre-existing parameters assures consistency and reliability in the findings. Consequently, it enhances the overall precision and efficacy of the fatigue analysis.

The section of the chamber where the ribs connect to the endplates is subject to high-stress levels, rendering it vulnerable to fatigue damage. A sub-model is extracted from the global model of the vacuum chamber, partitioned distances in Eq. (1) from shell bodies junctions according to the IIW recommendations [5]. This partitioning serves as a guideline for meshing, thus enabling the recording of nodal stress values during post-processing for fatigue analysis and the computation of hot spot stress using the LSE method.

This partitioned sub-model is illustrated in Figure 24. In total, three sub-models, meshed with 10-mm quadrilateral elements, are created for fatigue analysis using hot spot methods. This technique is also adopted to generate solid sub-models for fracture mechanics analysis, necessitating a much finer mesh,

particularly in proximity to semi-elliptical crack tips. These solid sub-models are essential in calculating the magnitude of the stress intensity factor at crack tips.

Figure 24 – Sub-model representation of end rib connections

4.7. Plants records

4.7.1. Number of cycles

The number of cycles for entry/exit chambers in two different plants (Bascharage, Luxembourg and Czestochowa, Poland) was calculated based on the available data of the plants according to their full cycle time, uptime percentage and lifetime. These parameters vary during the functional time of the chambers, therefore, the number of cycles for different periods is calculated and aggregated to represent the total number of cycles over the entire lifetime of the chambers. Up until the conclusion of 2022, the Bascharage and Czestochowa plants had respectively undergone 10 and 14 million full cycles under atmospheric pressure.

4.7.2. Fatigue damage assessments

Owing to the varying degrees of damage and different management practices in the two aforementioned plants, different fatigue damage inspection patterns are applied to the chambers installed in these facilities. For the Bascharage plant, data from visual observations are solely available

following 10 million cycles. However, the fatigue damages in the Czestochowa plant were under continuous monitoring due to its critical situation.

Visual inspection data is recorded at 5 million cycles for the Czestochowa plant. Subsequently, starting from 9 million cycles, the chambers undergo regular inspections for fatigue cracks at intervals of approximately 0.5 million cycles. During each inspection, the cracks are assessed using three distinct non-destructive testing (NDT) methods including ultrasonic testing, magnetic particle testing, and penetrant testing.

5. Results

Redacted version – Guardian® Industries can provide the complete report upon request. Interested parties can contact a member of the Guardian R&D team in the headquarter of Guardian Europe S.à.r.l. in Bertrange, Luxembourg.

6. Re-design of the chamber for improved fatigue resistance

Redacted version – Guardian® Industries can provide the complete report upon request. Interested parties can contact a member of the Guardian R&D team in the headquarter of Guardian Europe S.à.r.l. in Bertrange, Luxembourg.

7. Fatigue performance of original and re-designed chamber

Redacted version – Guardian® Industries can provide the complete report upon request. Interested parties can contact a member of the Guardian R&D team in the headquarter of Guardian Europe S.à.r.l. in Bertrange, Luxembourg.

8. Second-generation of entry/exit vacuum chamber without hydraulic jacks

Redacted version – Guardian® Industries can provide the complete report upon request. Interested parties can contact a member of the Guardian R&D team in the headquarter of Guardian Europe S.à.r.l. in Bertrange, Luxembourg.

9. Conclusion

A 3D model of the entry/exit vacuum chamber has been developed using Autodesk Inventor®, based on available data and on-site measurements. This model is geometrically processed for FE analysis using ANSYS® SpaceClaim [14] software, including the extraction of surface bodies for shell analysis. The model is subsequently imported into ANSYS® Mechanical [15] for further FE analysis. Results are validated against deflection measurements and observed fatigue crack patterns. In addition, an evaluation is conducted to ascertain the influence of pre-existing fatigue damages on the structural integrity of the chamber during maintenance periods when the chamber is open, thus addressing any potential safety concerns. The impact of hydraulic jack engagement on the fatigue behaviour of the vacuum chambers is also assessed. Shell-to-shell and shell-to-solid sub-models with refined mesh are created to evaluate fatigue behaviour of vacuum chamber using hot spot and LEFM methods. Lastly, a re-design of the vacuum chamber is undertaken inspired by topology optimization, sensitivity analysis and fatigue behaviour to relieve the stress concentration at hot spots, thereby prolonging the fatigue life of entry/exit vacuum chamber.

Here are some highlights of the findings.

- While the re-designed chamber lid is slightly lighter than the original one, the stress levels at hot spots are approximately half of those found in the original model.
- The re-designed entry/exit vacuum chamber with hydraulic jacks exhibits a fatigue life 45 times greater than the original design. This factor of improvement is derived by calculating the ratio of the *lowest* fatigue life values noted in the fatigue-prone zones of the original design to that of the re-designed chamber.
- Due to system's capacity for stress redistribute after stiffness change due to fatigue damage, the minimum fatigue life might not accurately reflect the realistic operational lifespan of the vacuum chamber.
- The reengineered vacuum chamber with hydraulic jacks exhibits an *average* increase in fatigue life that is 24 times greater at fatigue-prone zones, calculated by averaging the fatigue life improvements across these areas.
- While the minimum fatigue life across different zones can adequately indicate the lifespan before crack inspection is needed, the average increase in fatigue life might serve as a more realistic parameter for determining the actual operational lifespan.
- While some of the fatigue damages compromise the structural integrity of vacuum chambers, others have minimal impact on system stability. Therefore, it is important to simulate the damage to understand its impact on the safety of a structural system.

- If geometric complexities cannot be eliminated, introducing additional system stiffness can help reduce stress concentration at hot spots.
- Increasing the height of the ribs proved more effective in reducing stress concentration compared to increasing the thickness of the ribs.

This study has certain limitations that could influence the results. For instance, in line with the IIW recommendations [5], a conservative approach was adopted where the mean stress effect was not considered for welded parts. Moreover, the effects of weld throat size, intermittent welding, and one-sided fillet welding were not taken into account in the fatigue analysis using the hot spot method with shell models. It is also noteworthy that the IIW S-N curves do not make distinctions based on steel grades.

Ultimately, the damage-tolerant design approach for the vacuum chamber necessitates periodic crack inspections by trained inspectors to ensure the chamber's safe and smooth operation. This can be costly. Even after detecting cracks, specialist engineering teams with expertise in fracture mechanics and fatigue analysis must assess the damage's extent and make repair/no-repair decisions. Identifying appropriate fatigue repair methods can pose significant challenges and be time-consuming for engineers, as each damage may require a unique repair approach. However, adopting the fatigue-resistant design approach can obviate the need for periodic fatigue inspections, thus relieving the engineering team's burden.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Sub-models with LSE method

This section illustrates the sub-models generated, partitioned, and analysed according to LSE method.

Figure 25 – Sub-modelling for Zones A, B and J – Left: Illustration of stress distribution; Right: Partitioning for application of the LSE method

Figure 26 - Sub-modelling for Zone C – Left: Illustration of stress distribution; Right: Partitioning for application of the LSE method

Figure 27 - Sub-modelling for Zones D, I, G and H – Left: Illustration of stress distribution; Right: Partitioning for application of the LSE method

Figure 28 – Principal stress levels at Zone D and I representing top and bottom brackets of hydraulic jacks

Figure 29 – Principal stress level at Zone E with 10 mm mesh size

Appendix B: Examination of alternative design concepts not incorporated into the final re-design

Presented within this appendix are several design modifications, specifically tested with the intent of improving fatigue performance within the entry/exit vacuum chamber. These modifications generally adopt a localized approach, aiming to refine specific chamber details for enhanced fatigue resilience.

Despite their potential benefits, these design ideas were not adopted for the final re-design. The primary justification for this decision stems from the fact that while these modifications often successfully alleviate stress concentration at targeted hot spots, they unintentionally introduce new stress hot spots in other regions of the vacuum chamber.

This situation underscores the intricate complexities involved in stress relief techniques within design for improved fatigue resistance. It is vital to approach these re-designs with thorough caution to avoid remedying one issue while inadvertently engendering new ones elsewhere.

- *Circular Cut-out at corners*

A recognized fatigue detail in bridge design involves incorporating circular cut-outs at corners to mitigate stress concentration in these specific zones. This approach has been adapted and applied to the intersection of the chamber lid channels and volume-reducer steps in the vacuum chamber design. These areas, as previously discussed, are particularly susceptible to fatigue cracks.

Figure 30 illustrates the implementation of the circular cut-out detail on the sub-model, and the subsequent stress distribution following this modification. The centre of the circle forming the cut-out

is intentionally positioned 10 mm away from the junction of the plates. This design choice aims to prevent the formation of acute angles at the edges of the circular cut-out.

Figure 30 – Circular cut-out: Left) Schematic view of the cut-out configuration and partitioning for the application of the LSE method - Right) Stress distribution after modification

Two different circular cut-out radii, 25 mm and 45 mm, are applied in this fatigue detail, as depicted in Figure 31 and Figure 32. While these modifications slightly diminish the stress concentration from 134 MPa to 113 MPa for the 25-mm cut-out and 130 MPa for the 45-mm cut-out, they induce high stress concentration at the edges of the circular cut-out. The magnitudes of these stress concentrations reach 228 MPa and 255 MPa in models with the 25-mm and 45-mm cut-outs, respectively. This data suggests that the adopted configuration for implementing this fatigue detail may not be suitable for this specific vacuum chamber.

Figure 31 – Von-Mises stress distribution at the corner: Left) Original configuration Right) Circular cut-out with radius of 25 mm

Figure 32 - Von-Mises stress distribution at the corner: Left) Original configuration Right) Circular cut-out with radius of 45 mm

The concept of a circular cut-out has been reintroduced with a different design approach, as displayed in Figure 33. In this configuration, the connection between the channel and volume-reducer steps is eliminated, leaving behind a corner in the channel that is then rounded with a radius of 30 mm. Furthermore, in this design, the edge of the channel is maintained at a distance of 30 mm from the surface of the volume-reducer steps. This specific design adjustment is implemented to mitigate the stress concentration identified at the edges of the circular cut-out in the preceding configuration.

Figure 33 – Schematic view of the cut-out configuration with extended de-attachment

This design detail completely relieves the stress concentration at the corner, bringing it down to 33 MPa. However, areas of elevated stress are still discernible within this detail, specifically at the circular cut-out and the junction where the channel meets the side plate, as illustrated in Figure 34. Although this detail effectively alleviates stress concentration at the corner and avoids the problematic stress concentrations at the edges of the circular cut-out seen in the previous design, it introduces two new

stress concentration areas. This outcome renders this particular detail unsuitable for application to the vacuum chamber.

Figure 34 – Von-Mises stress distribution after application of extended circular cut-out

- Secondary beams at longitudinal direction

An evaluated method for enhancing the fatigue behaviour of the entry/exit vacuum chamber involves the integration of secondary channels in a longitudinal direction, thereby augmenting the stiffness of the chamber without necessitating an increase in its height. This modification specifically targets the mitigation of corner fatigue cracks by increasing the chamber's longitudinal stiffness. The increased stiffness serves to counteract excessive deformation at the corners during the pump-down phase when the chamber walls flex inward due to the pressure differential.

The initial modification involves the addition of two extra channels on each side of the channel, arranged perpendicularly to the primary channels as illustrated in Figure 35. These additional structures, attached to the upper half of the primary channels, effectively mitigate corner stress, reducing it to approximately half of the initial values. However, these additions create stress hot spots at the junctions with the primary channels, as shown in Figure 36.

The stress concentration within these hot spots may be lessened by employing internal stiffeners at the junctions of the primary and secondary channels. Nevertheless, this technique necessitates extensive welding, which not only escalates the cost but also creates a new heat-affected zone (HAZ), potentially exacerbating the fatigue performance of the chamber.

Figure 35 – Extra secondary beams in the longitudinal direction

Figure 36 – Stress concentration at the intersection of primary and secondary ribs

Continuous secondary channels have been incorporated along the length of the vacuum chamber, in an attempt to alleviate the stress concentration at the intersection of the primary and secondary channels. The intent is to create a more consistent pattern that facilitates load transfer in the longitudinal direction, as illustrated in Figure 37. FE analysis suggests that the introduction of these centrally positioned secondary ribs does not mitigate the stress concentration at the junction of the primary and secondary beams. However, the analysis indicates a reduction in stress concentrations at other critical areas. Figure

38 depicts the von Mises stress distribution subsequent to the integration of continuous secondary ribs into the vacuum chamber.

Figure 37 – Continuous secondary channels in the longitudinal direction

Figure 38 – Von Mises stress distribution following the addition of continuous secondary ribs

In an effort to reduce the stress concentration at the ribs intersection, the continuous secondary channel has been laterally shifted, as illustrated Figure 39. Given that the primary channels undergo maximum stress at their midspan, the introduction of a HAZ in this area through welding may adversely impact the chamber's fatigue performance. While the intersection of the primary and secondary ribs at the sides also exhibits high stress concentration, the overall stress level in this zone is relatively low. This suggests that the positioning of the secondary channel at the sides of the primary channel introduces resistance to the primary channels' rotation. Consequently, this generates localized torsional forces at the intersections of the ribs. In other words, the primary channels, which tend to rotate at the sides as opposed to the central location (where deflection-induced rotation is not experienced), encounter resistance from the secondary beams. This resistance against rotation, in turn, creates torsional force and thus results in stress concentration. Figure 40 provides a visual representation of the von Mises stress distribution following the lateral repositioning of the secondary channels within the vacuum chamber.

Figure 39 – Shifting the secondary ribs to the sides of the channel

Figure 40 – Von Mises stress distribution following to shifting the secondary channels to the sides

- Introducing box beams at sides

In order to enhance the fatigue performance of the entry/exit chamber at the sides, a box beam is integrated on one side of the chamber where the ribs were initially affixed to the side plates, as depicted in Figure 41. The addition of this box beam serves multiple purposes: it reduces the stress concentration at the juncture of the ribs and side plates, provides a platform for reliable attachment of supports to the chamber, and introduces structural elements capable of bearing loads in the longitudinal direction.

Compared to the prior side plates, the box beam section possesses significantly greater torsional stiffness. This additional torsional stiffness counteracts deflection-induced rotation at the ends of the channel sections, leading to the generation of torsional forces at these endpoints, as shown in Figure 42. Although the magnitude of this newly formed stress concentration is comparable to that of the previous design detail, it does not lead to an improvement in fatigue performance and is thus not incorporated in the final re-design.

Figure 41 – Incorporation of a box beam on one side of the vacuum chamber

Figure 42 – Von Mises stress distribution after incorporating the box beam

To permit unobstructed rotation of the rib end sections, their connection has been eliminated by introducing a small gap between the channel end and the box beam, as illustrated in Figure 43. With this modification, the channel section end can rotate freely, accommodating deflection-induced rotation of the ribs. However, this change leads to the generation of substantial shear forces at the connection between the chamber and the plate beneath it, as shown in Figure 44. This emergent stress concentration renders the modification unsuitable for fatigue design.

Figure 43 – Detaching the box beam from the channels

Figure 44 – Von Mises stress distribution after detaching the ribs from the box beam

○ Separation of hydraulic jack from the main body

The bottom bracket of the hydraulic jack is susceptible to fatigue-induced cracking when the jack is engaged during the operational state of the entry/exit vacuum chamber. The occurrence of such fatigue cracks significantly endangers the safety of plant personnel during maintenance periods. The stress concentration resulting from these cracks can be alleviated through the detachment of the hydraulic jack from the main structure. This disconnection, achievable via the removal of welding details, results in a reduction of stress levels at the hot spot to less than half their initial values.

However, such a change necessitates alterations to the support details. Following this modification, the weight of the hydraulic chamber will transfer directly to the support; without suitable adjustment, this could induce high stress levels in the support structure, as shown in Figure 45. Although this modification yields promising results, it has not been included in the final re-design. This is because the stress levels at the hot spot in the re-designed model have already been reduced to acceptable values; further reduction is unnecessary, especially considering that this change requires the development of new support details.

Figure 45 – Von Mises stress distribution in the bottom bracket of hydraulic jacks: Left) Effect of detaching the hydraulic jack; Right) Original condition with the hydraulic jack welded to the main body

○ The effect of supports placement and number

The entry/exit vacuum chamber is mounted on four supports in both the original and second-generation designs. The purpose of these supports is to bear the chamber's weight and transfer the load to the ground. In the second-generation chamber, these supports are positioned beneath the final channels, whereas in the original chamber design, they are located under the penultimate¹ rows.

Figure 46 illustrates the impact of this support positioning on the stress distribution within the second-generation entry/exit vacuum chamber. The first figure depicts the stress distribution with the original positioning of the supports. The following figure, however, illustrates the stress distribution when the supports' location is shifted to the next rows.

The repositioning of the supports in the newer design mildly mitigates the stress concentration at the junction of the mechanical pipes. However, given that the overall shift in stress distribution due to this adjustment is minimal, the original positioning of the supports is retained in the final re-design.

¹ Next to the last

B: Static Structural Tudela

Equivalent Stress 2

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress - Bottom

Unit: MPa

Time: 1 s

Max: 244.36

Min: 0

(a)

B: Static Structural Tudela

Equivalent Stress 2

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress - Bottom

Unit: MPa

Time: 1 s

Max: 245.35

Min: 0

(b)

Figure 46 – The influence of the supports positioning on stress distribution: a) Original placement at last rows b) Modified placement at penultimate rows

An investigation into the impact of support quantity on the stress distribution of the second-generation entry/exit vacuum chamber was conducted by introducing four additional supports beneath the central channels. Figure 47 displays the tensile principal stress distribution for the vacuum chamber with both four and eight supports. The incorporation of the four extra supports yields no significant alteration in

stress distribution. Thus, it can be inferred that the placement and quantity of supports have a minimal effect on the vacuum chamber's structural response to cyclic atmospheric pressure.

(a)

(b)

Figure 47 – The impact of supports number on stress distribution: a) Four supports; b) Eight supports

Appendix C: The Limitations of LSE method in complex structures: The misconception of stress increase towards weld toe or junction

As discussed earlier, the primary aim of the LSE method is to reasonably estimate stress values at critical hot spots for fatigue analysis. This method extrapolates from a specific distance from the weld toe in solid modelling, or from the intersections of the plates in shell modelling. The fundamental assumption underpinning this method is an increase in stress magnitude as the intersection is approached, which is typically valid in isolated specimens.

However, findings from this study suggest that in large-scale models with complex geometries, this assumption does not invariably hold true, due to the complex state of stress within the structure. For instance, Figure 48 displays a construction line adjacent to the intersection of the steel plates, extending from '0.4t' to t distance from the intersection, where 't' represents the plate thickness. While an increase in stress magnitude is typically expected when approaching the section, the Figure 48 reveals a contradiction: stress values at a t distance exceed those at a 0.4t distance.

Figure 48 – Construction line representing the stress magnitude at specific distance from an intersection

Likewise, Figure 49 depicts the stress distribution in proximity to the intersection between the channels and side plates in the chamber lid and body. Interestingly, the figure indicates a decrease in stress magnitude as one approaches the intersection. A comparable pattern is observable near the connection

of the chamber to the underlying plate as illustrated in Figure 50. This pattern suggests that while stress values tend to increase when approaching intersections in isolated specimens, this assumption may not hold true for more complex geometries in real-world structures.

Figure 49 – Stress distribution next the intersection of channel to the side plates: Left) Chamber lid Right) Chamber body

Figure 50 – Stress distribution next to the channel intersection with the plate beneath